

Analysis of The Carpentries Long-Term Impact Survey

*Kari L. Jordan**

July 17th, 2018

Contents

Overview	1
Workshop Content	5
Workshop Impact	5
Programming Usage Pre- and Post-Workshop	6
Workshop Impact	7
Recommending Carpentries Workshops	9
Call to Action	9

Overview

To date, 621 learners have completed the Carpentries Long-Term Impact Survey between March 22, 2017 and May 29, 2018. The average amount of time spent completing this survey is six minutes, and it carries an 80% completion rate. The survey was created in March 2017, and data is collected bi-annually. The results of this analysis are cumulative. We invite the community to run their own analyses. All of the data and source code are available on GitHub.

A special thanks to Ben Markwick, François Michonneau and others who helped write the code used in this report.

Demographics

This section includes demographics for survey respondents broken down by:

- Country
- Field and Career Stage
- Gender and Racial/Ethnic Identity

Breakdown of Respondents by Country

*<https://twitter.com/drkariljordan>

Breakdown of Respondents by Field and Career Stage

Respondents Field of Research/Work/Study	n	%
Life Sciences	197	35.9
Biomedical/Health Sciences	122	22.2
Agricultural or Environmental Sciences	88	16.0
Physical Sciences	61	11.1
Earth Sciences	52	9.5
Engineering	47	8.6
Mathematics or Statistics	44	8.0
Computer Science	43	7.8
Library Sciences	30	5.5
Social Sciences	28	5.1
Humanities	20	3.6
Business	8	1.5

Provided below is a table of participant counts in each category. Multiple selection was possible.

Breakdown of Respondents by Gender and Racial/Ethnic Identity

Gender Identity and Racial/Ethnic Identity was added to the survey during the second round of data collection, so these numbers do not reflect the cumulative amount of respondents.

Gender Identity	n	%
Female	22	69
Male	10	31

Racial/Ethnic Identity	n	%
Asian	6	18
Black or African American	3	9
Hispanic or Latino(a)	2	6
I prefer not to say.	3	9
White	20	59

Respondent Engagement in Workshops and Surveys

This section includes the following:

- Number of Workshops Attended
- Time Since Attending a Workshop
- Last Carpentries Workshop Attended
- Survey Engagement

Number of Workshops Attended

Some respondents attend multiple workshops

Time Since Attending a Workshop

Majority Respondents Attended a Workshop One Year Ago

Last Carpentries Workshop Attended

Workshop Respondents Attended	n	%
Data Carpentry	24	30
Library Carpentry	5	6
Software Carpentry	48	60
I don't know.	3	4

Survey Engagement

Learners Taking Survey for First Time	n	%
Yes	86	88

Learners Taking Survey for First Time	n	%
No	3	3
I don't know.	9	9

Workshop Content

Learners were asked to check all that applies to indicate what content was covered at the last Carpentries workshop they completed. The tables below provide this information, and combinations of tools covered most often.

Content Covered in Respondents Workshops	n	%
Git	411	26
Python	329	21
Unix Shell	327	21
R	229	15
SQL	148	9
OpenRefine	38	2
I don't remember.	32	2
Spreadsheets	27	2
Cloud Computing	17	1
MATLAB	6	0
Mercurial	3	0

Frequency of Tools Covered	n	%
Git Python Unix Shell	105	16.9
Git Python	44	7.1
Git Python SQL Unix Shell	41	6.6
Git R Unix Shell	35	5.6
Git R	25	4.0
Git Python R Unix Shell	21	3.4
Git Unix Shell	19	3.1
R	19	3.1
Git Python SQL	17	2.7
Python	14	2.3

Workshop Impact

We are interested in knowing what behaviors learners adopt as a result of completing a Carpentries workshop. Respondents were asked to check all that apply.

Behaviors Respondents Adopted	n	%
Using programming languages like R or Python, or the command line to automate repetitive tasks.	312	66.2
Using version control to manage code.	208	44.2
Reusing code.	201	42.7
Sharing code or data publicly on places like GitHub or FigShare.	147	31.2

Behaviors Respondents Adopted	n	%
Using databases, scripts and queries to manage large data sets.	143	30.4
Transforming step-by-step workflows into scripts or functions.	137	29.1
Using version control to collaborate online (in public or private repositories).	136	28.9
Developing a data management and analysis plan.	84	17.8

The table below provides behaviors adopted by career stage..

Behaviors	Academic	Graduate			Undergraduate	
	Research Staff	Faculty	Student	Industry	Postdoc	Student
Developing a data management and analysis plan.	10.7	14.1	17.5	21.3	12.1	0.0
Improving data management and project organization.	40.0	50.0	39.7	45.9	40.4	0.0
Reusing code.	38.7	32.8	37.6	36.1	34.3	18.2
Sharing code or data publicly on places like GitHub or FigShare.	28.0	26.6	23.8	29.5	26.3	27.3
Transforming step-by-step workflows into scripts or functions.	26.7	17.2	28.0	26.2	27.3	18.2
Using databases, scripts and queries to manage large data sets.	22.7	18.8	25.9	29.5	31.3	9.1
Using programming languages like R or Python, or the command line to automate repetitive tasks.	61.3	48.4	60.8	59.0	58.6	27.3
Using version control to collaborate online (in public or private repositories).	26.7	29.7	18.5	45.9	21.2	36.4
Using version control to manage code.	44.0	39.1	31.7	60.7	31.3	27.3

Programming Usage Pre- and Post-Workshop

Compared to before completing a Carpentries workshop, we want to know how often respondents used programming languages (R, Python, etc.), databases (Access, SQL, etc.), version control software and/or the shell. Below we compare pre/post programming usage.

Workshop Impact

The statements below reflect ways in which completing a Carpentries may impact learners. We asked respondents to rate level of agreement with these statements:

- **Reproducible:** I have made my analyses more reproducible as a result of completing the workshop.
- **Recognition:** I have received professional recognition for my work as a result of using the tools I learned at the workshop.
- **Productivity:** My research productivity has improved as a result of completing the workshop.
- **Motivation:** I have been motivated to seek more knowledge about the tools I learned at the workshop.
- **Confidence:** I have gained confidence in working with data as a result of completing the workshop.
- **Coding:** I have improved my coding practices as a result of completing the workshop.
- **Career:** I have used skills I learned at the workshop to advance my career.

The heatmap below provides a breakdown of responses.

We are also interested in understanding what impact our workshops have on respondents long-term. This includes the following:

- Change in Confidence
- Usage of Tools for Research and/or Work
- Contributions to Academic Writing
- Involvement in the Carpentries
- Continuous Learning

Change in Confidence

We asked respondents to rate their change in confidence in the tools that were covered during their Carpentries workshops compared to before the workshop. The figure below provides a synopsis.

Usage of Tools for Research and/or Work

If respondents are using the tools they learned in a Carpentries workshop, we want to know how they are helping. Respondents were asked to check all that apply.

How Tools Covered Help Respondents	n	%
They are improving my overall efficiency.	291	60.4
They are improving my ability to analyze data.	259	53.7
They are improving my ability to manage data.	240	49.8
I am not using the tools I learned.	70	14.5
The tools I learned have not helped me with my work.	35	7.3

Contributions to Academic Writing

We are also interested in knowing whether completing a Carpentries workshop contributed to writing of a research article, thesis, dissertation, or grant proposal.

Have Tools Contributed to Respondents' Writing?	n	%
No.	241	46.4
Not sure.	137	26.4
Yes.	141	27.2

Involvement with the Carpentries

We asked respondents to indicate their involvement in the Carpentries community since completing a Carpentry workshop. Respondents were asked to check all that apply.

Respondents Involvement with The Carpentries	n	%
Subscribed to the newsletter.	152	46
Became a workshop helper.	46	14
Became a Carpentry instructor.	38	11
Contributed to a Carpentry lesson.	29	9
Attended at least one community call.	27	8
Joined a mentoring group.	17	5
Participated in a Twitter chat.	15	5
Joined a committee.	9	3

Continuous Learning

Which of the following learning activities (for data management and analysis) have you participated in since completing a Carpentry workshop? Check all that apply.

Respondents' Continuous Learning Activities	n	%
Used non-Carpentry self-guided material.	155	35
Used self-guided Carpentry lesson material.	90	20
Participated in an in-person short course.	72	16
Participated in an online short course.	55	12
Participated in a Meetup.	39	9
Participated in a semester long course.	30	7

Recommending Carpentries Workshops

Have respondents recommended a Carpentry workshop to a friend or colleague? Responses provided below.

Respondents who Recommended a Workshop	n	%
Yes.	363	75
No.	71	15
I don't remember.	47	10

Call to Action

How can we improve this analysis? Submit an issue or pull request!